

**BIOCHEMICAL CHANGES IN THE ATHLETE'S BODY
DURING OVERTRAINING****Bokiyeva Gulnoza Habibullayevna****PhD in Biological Sciences Alfraganus University,
Tashkent, Uzbekistan****<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17608273>****ARTICLE INFO**Received: 12th November 2025Accepted: 13th November 2025Online: 14th November 2025**KEYWORDS***training, physical activity,
creatine phosphokinase,
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alanine aminotransferase.***ABSTRACT**

This study examines the general patterns and specific features of changes in the activity of numerous enzymes in an athlete's body during physical exercise. Elevated enzyme activity results from biochemical alterations in cells triggered by intensive or prolonged muscle work. Enzyme activity induced by short-term physical exertion is characterized by a rapid return to baseline levels during rest. A sustained increase in enzyme activity signals excessively high training loads. In sports practice, the activities of creatine phosphokinase (CPK), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), and alanine aminotransferase (ALT) are most frequently measured to evaluate athletes' functional status and the effects of training.

Creatine phosphokinase (CPK) is an intracellular enzyme that catalyzes the synthesis and degradation of creatine phosphate by transferring a phosphate group from creatine phosphate to ADP (adenosine diphosphate). This process enables muscles to receive a substantial amount of energy within a short timeframe [1]. Research indicates that creatine kinase levels are significantly higher in athletes participating in strength-based sports. The elevated CPK activity in these athletes is linked to the predominance of the creatine phosphokinase pathway in ATP resynthesis for energy supply during loads [2; 3; 4]. CPK plays a crucial role in the energy metabolism of muscle and nervous tissues. Under normal conditions, serum CPK activity ranges from 40 to 200 U/L. During anaerobic exercises, peak activity is observed 5 minutes after completion of muscle activity (e.g., in sprints up to 400 m). In short-duration, maximal-intensity loads, CPK activity metrics are used to assess training intensity or identify signs of overtraining [2; 5; 6; 3]. Following prolonged endurance exercises involving high-intensity oxidative processes—such as marathon running, 30–50 km cross-country skiing, multi-day cycling races, or triathlon events—serum CPK activity rises 24–28 hours post-exercise and remains elevated for 3–6 days [5; 6; 3]. Investigations into CPK dynamics after resistance training with weights [7] reveal that enzyme activity approximately doubles (100% increase) within 8 hours, reaching peak values between 24 and 96 hours, depending on the exercise type and individual physiological characteristics of the athletes [8; 7; 9]. Short-term cooling interventions, including cold water immersion [10], contrast therapy [11], and cryotherapy [12], help mitigate the risk of post-exercise CPK elevation. The

magnitude of physical loads induces diverse biochemical changes in muscles, blood, and internal organs.

Aspartate aminotransferase (AST) and alanine aminotransferase (ALT) are intracellular enzymes found in the liver, skeletal muscles, cardiac muscle, and kidneys. Elevated ALT and AST activities in blood plasma indicate cellular damage in these tissues. Both enzymes participate in amino acid metabolism: AST catalyzes the reversible transfer of an amino group from L-aspartate to α -ketoglutarate, while ALT performs the same for L-alanine [5; 6; 3; 13]. These enzymes are confined to organ tissue cells and enter the bloodstream only due to injury or pathological disruption. Normal reference ranges are ALT: 3–26 U/L and AST: 6–25 U/L. AST exhibits the highest activity in the heart, liver, muscles, and kidneys, whereas ALT is predominantly concentrated in the liver with minimal presence elsewhere. AST levels rise primarily in cardiac and skeletal muscle pathologies, while ALT increases in acute hepatitis. Consequently, AST serves as a marker of myocardial injury, and ALT indicates acute liver or biliary tract disorders. AST and ALT remain within normal limits in angina pectoris. In infants, elevated ALT and AST may occur physiologically without pathological significance. In athletes, increased activity of these enzymes enables early detection of metabolic disturbances in the liver, heart, and muscles; assessment of exercise tolerance; and evaluation of pharmacological interventions.

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